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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Project FreeWheel “Lifecycle-reconfigurable Smart Mobility Platform to enable autonomous and cost-effective personalized solutions for social inclusion of disabled and elderly while leveraging AM technologies” (Grant Agreement number 768908) is a four year project started on October the 1st 2017. The project has the main objectives of:

Promoting social inclusion of disabled and elderly by developing a smart mobility platform based on a reconfigurable autonomous unit to ease individual mobility in urban environment.

Satisfying the need of customization both for the disabled and for the unit by implementing a modular reconfigurable concept based on standard low-cost modules and on ultra-customized interfaces to be produced by additive manufacturing.

Making affordable the lifecycle cost of the above-mentioned mobility service/product by implementing an innovative business model.

The project is structured in nine work packages. This report focuses on the activities undertaken in Year two of the project, which revolved mainly around the design of the motorising solution (work package 3) and the definition of the service (work package 4). Within work packages (WP) 5 and 6, the process and production infrastructure for the FreeWheel unit have been analysed and set up ready for validation. The above activities were complemented by the development of the Lifecycle Engineering Platform and the definition of the FreeWheel Round Robin Parts in WP3, and the set up of the integration of the motorising solution with the rack for the storage of the FreeWheel motorising units and the digital platform supporting the mobility services (WP7). Activities on FreeWheel awareness raising have continued with an acceleration on activities on exploitation of the results (WP9). A short description of activities expected within the next year for the WPs active or to be initiated is also provided.

WP3, nearing its completion at the end of Year Two, had the main objective of designing the mechanic and electronic aspects of the FreeWheel motorising solution. The mechanic solution was designed considering the Technical Development Objectives, finalised within WP2, which summarise the expectations of the end-users matched with the technical capabilities of the latest manufacturing technologies. The electronic part of the solution was designed considering the service features required.

The manufacturing of the FreeWheel solution’s mechanic components is supported by the latest metal and polymer Additive Manufacturing technologies and processes, integrated by a platform (the Life Cycle Engineering platform) supporting the digital exchange of information from end user through to production. Leveraging the knowledge of the process (WP5) and advanced manufacturing facilities (WP6) within the team, the motorising solution has been designed as an integration of standard, commercial components and customised parts. The latter are being checked for structural performance and manufacturability for validation and manufacturing optimisation in Year Three.

WP4 focused on the design of the service, translating into features and digital touchpoints the likes and dislikes of users’ experiences collected during WP2. The outcome of the work package is a blueprint of the service, which also takes into account the Service Design Objectives defined within WP2, and a roadmap to ensure the successful set up and undertaking of the demonstration activities in Year Three. The team is now focusing on finalising the app accompanying the user from the subscription to the FreeWheel service through and after the rental.

WP9 focused on the dissemination and awareness raising of FreeWheel project results with attendance to events and conferences and publication of articles and papers in proceedings and journals. The team accelerated activities on exploitation of the main result of the project with two dedicated workshops shaping the business model and starting the development of the business plan.

The annual gender equality monitoring activity highlighted that project FreeWheel has kept its nearly 50:50 split in female and male team members, already achieved at the end of Year One.

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1 Introduction

Project FreeWheel “Lifecycle-reconfigurable Smart Mobility Platform to enable autonomous and cost-effective personalized solutions for social inclusion of disabled and elderly while leveraging AM technologies” (Grant Agreement number 768908) is a three year project started on October the 1st 2017 funded by the Horizon 2020 programme under the call Factory of the Future 2017 - topic 10 “New technologies and life cycle management for reconfigurable and reusable customised products”.

FreeWheel general objectives are to:

Promote social inclusion of disabled and elderly by developing a smart mobility platform based on a reconfigurable autonomous unit to ease individual mobility in urban environment. The versatility of FreeWheel solution allows compensating for the presence of physical barriers, helping to extend the degree of access to contexts and autonomy of the person with disability in an increasing number of environments.

Satisfy the need of customization both for the disabled and for the unit by implementing a modular reconfigurable concept based on standard low-cost modules and on ultra-customized interfaces to be produced by additive manufacturing. Modularity, by using low cost standard modules (engine, gears, control unit, HMI, etc.) and highly customized interface (body to unit, engine to unit, unit to infrastructure, etc.); Reconfigurability, by allowing an ease re-use of standard modules in different products (e.g. same electrification module in different unit fleets, differently customized to the surrounding environment);

Make affordable the lifecycle cost of the above-mentioned mobility service/product by implementing an innovative business model that:

- offers the mobility as a service separating the use from the ownership of the units,
- leverages manufacturing dematerialization to reduce lead time and investment cost, in particular Additive Manufacturing technologies to reduce the cost of person-to-unit personalization and unit-to-infrastructure customization,
- shares investment, cost and revenues all along the relevant stakeholders along the mobility value chain: disabled, urban centre, infrastructure owners, vehicle integrators, service providers, components suppliers, Additive Manufacturing centres. An affordable synergetic investment in the infrastructure is necessary to make simple and affordable the positioning and navigation system (WP6, value chain),
- leverages product reconfigurability, achieved thanks to product modularity, to cover large production volumes through the sum of small batches of highly customised products whose configuration is supported by a co-engineering digital platform involving players belonging to the entire supply chain,
- extends the lifecycle of product by re-use, re-manufacturing and possible upgrade of components.

The project is implemented by a Consortium of ten organisations including SMEs, Universities, Public Entities, NGOs from Italy, Switzerland, Spain and Greece.

The work is structured in nine work packages illustrated below, with links to the objectives of the project.

Figure 1 FreeWheel work packages and links with project objectives

During its second year, the project reached the peak of its technical development, with seven out of nine work packages active. WP2 ended at Month 12 while WP8 is gearing up for a start in Month 24. Early next year, work packages 3 and 4 will end in succession, followed by WP6 and 5 and then WP7. All the results of these WPs will flow into the Demonstration work package, while dissemination and exploitation activities within WP9 will pick up the pace.

This report summarises the activities undertaken within the active work packages identifying the main results achieved.

2 Work Package 1: Project Management

This WP covers the administrative and coordination aspects of the project. A separate, confidential, administrative and financial report on these aspects has been produced (Deliverable D1.5) for the European Commission.

FreeWheel project undertook a successful 18 months Review in March 2019 and the 5th General Assembly was held in Monopoli, Italy in September 2019.

3 Work Package 3 FreeWheel product design

3.1 OBJECTIVES

WP3 focuses on the design of the FreeWheel mobility mechanic and electronic solution consisting of the active module (the motor and the sensing apparatus) and the customised connectors for the mounting of the active module onto different wheelchairs. To support the customisation of the connectors and the interface with the production process and infrastructure, a Life Cycle Engineering platform is being developed, while the specific parts are being analysed for mechanical performance and manufacturability.

Summarising all the defined and most important features, the FreeWheel solution has to be at least:

- A completely autonomous vehicle
- Equipped with a complete set of proximity sensors or a visual system for the object detection and obstacle avoidance
- Lightweight and not bulky/uncomfortable device
- Able to move in indoor and outdoor ground conditions
- Equipped by several driving control solutions like a Joystick, a smartphone app or a touchscreen customized in function of the necessities
- Other HMI interfaces

MCHTronics leads this WP still ongoing, with major contributions from SUPSI, LMS and KUMO.

3.2 ACTIVITIES

WP3 activities focused on:

- the design of the mechanic parts of the solution, with the definition of the customised interfaces and connectors between commercial/standard components and different wheelchairs;
- the finalisation of the system of sensors mounted onto the motorising unit for the monitoring and control of the motor and the data collection serving specific features of the solution (autonomous navigation amongst others);
- the performance and manufacturability analysis of the customised connectors leveraging metal and polymer Additive Manufacturing technologies;
- the set up of the Life Cycle Engineering Platform supporting the customer in the identification of the customised connectors and the manufacturers in their production.

The solution developed is being investigated for patentability and it is therefore described in this document in general terms.

3.2.1 Mechanic solution

Work package 2 resulted in a list of Technical Design Objectives (TDOs, see public deliverable D2.3 – Technical and Services Objectives and Key Results KPIs¹) that fed into the specifications of the design, governed by considerations on the many geometrics parameters of a wheelchair. FreeWheel solution needs to be suitably designed to cater for the varying width of a wheelchair (models go from the 44cm width of a child chair to the 100cm-wide bariatric chairs), different wheel models and wheel camber etc. Furthermore, considering the structure and functioning of a typical wheelchair, as well as the pros and cons of current motorisation solutions, alternative drives were identified and evaluated for feasibility.

WP3 elected a Rear Wheels Direct Drive Device configuration for the FreeWheel solution, with a master and a slave device mounted directly on the wheels of the customer wheelchair. When the end user wishes to motorise their wheelchair, the motorising unit attaches (and detaches) to (from) special interfaces mounted permanently on the chair via customised connectors. The differences in geometry of the wheelchairs are managed in the design of the connectors, which are light and slim to minimise any burden on the wheelchair and its users

3.2.2 Electronic solution

The FreeWheel solution includes sensors and controls supporting the service offered by the motorised solution. The choice of the electronics takes into account the user requirements for compactness and lightweight while providing the advance features characterising the FreeWheel solution.

The FreeWheel electronic solution comprises of a core compact computer on one hand processing the information coming from the onboard sensors and on the other controlling the onboard motors and their battery. The hardware is supported by or feeds into algorithms supporting obstacle avoidance, self balancing and tracking/navigation.

3.2.3 Round Robin Parts definition

The customised connectors are being analysed for mechanical performance and AM technology manufacturability, while also considering the introduction of parametric design strategies to ease the definition (and foresee the performance) of connectors for new wheelchair models.

3.2.4 Lifecycle Engineering Platform

The Lifecycle Engineering Platform supports the digitalisation and sharing of technical information for a quick production of the FreeWheel customised connectors and speedy delivery to the new subscribers of the FreeWheel service. The CAD module under development offers different access levels to the wheelchair manufacturers, who can provide technical drawings of their models; to the FreeWheel engineers, to design custom connectors for the wheelchairs; and to the end users, who can identify their wheelchair models from the available library. This CAD module can be interfaced with a CAx platform managing the production process for additive manufacturing through Direct Energy Deposition and ablation.

¹ Also available from <http://www.freewheelproject.eu/documents-2/>

3.3 NEXT STEPS

The FreeWheel solution is to be validated in a controlled environment within WP8 in parallel with the finalisation of the rack development (WP7). The analysis on the customised connectors is to be finalised for validation through manufacturing trials (WP5 and WP6).

4 Work Package 4 FreeWheel service and digital touchpoints design

4.1 OBJECTIVES

WP4 has the main objectives of designing the FreeWheel service and designing and implementing the digital touchpoints to implement the service itself. This work package mirrors WP3, which is developing the physical part of the solution, and similarly to it, stems from the work of WP2, where Service Design Objectives were defined to inform the work of this work package.

4.2 ACTIVITIES

The work package was subdivided into four main activities:

- The definition of the service challenges, i.e. aspects or steps related to the delivery of the service that must be solved to ensure a correct delivery of the service;
- The definition of the service blueprint, i.e. a detailed mapping of the functionalities of the service
- The definition of the roadmap to achieve the demonstration of the service
- The development of the digital touchpoints supporting the delivery of the service

4.2.1 Service challenges

In this activity, the team reviewed the information collected during WP2 to identify the challenges the service must face and win in order to provide the most suitable experience to users. The challenges identified included for example ensuring that FreeWheel solution is used only by the category of motion impaired people it has been designed for, so to keep users safe; another challenge is to make sure that the interface for mounting the motorising solution is mounted correctly. The responses to such design challenges are solutions incorporated either in the digital part of the service (e.g. a self-check through the app) or in the physical unit or at the rack (e.g. the delivery of the personalised interface at a rental location of choice where trained personnel will mount the connectors to the wheelchair).

4.2.2 Service blueprint

The blueprint of the FreeWheel service maps the relationships between different service components (people, props (physical or digital evidence), and processes) that are directly tied to touchpoints in a specific customer journey. The map corresponds to a specific customer journey and specific customer goals associated to that journey. It also describes the underlying resources and processes — seen and unseen to the customer — that make it possible. Within this blueprint, the team describes not only the service as it might develop for a user but also the timing and roles within the ecosystem supporting backstage the delivery of the service itself.

4.2.3 Implementation roadmap

With the map of the service and supporting activities defined, the team was able to describe the activities required to ensure the service will be implemented appropriately in the final demonstration of the FreeWheel solution at the end of the project. Considering the list of features associated with each node of the service blueprint, the team collaboratively defined the minimum viable solution, the development expected for the demonstrator and the full implementation level. As the previous task, this activity also allowed the team to scope out the possible next steps of development for the FreeWheel solution in terms of full commercial offering, which is valid information also for the exploitation activities within WP9.

4.2.4 Digital touchpoints

This activity, to be concluded early in Year Three of the project, concerns the development of the mobile app complementing the motorising unit for the delivery of the FreeWheel service. The app includes steps such as subscription, booking of the motorising unit, rental management, driving the motor in manual mode, and additional features such as mapping and route selection.

4.3 NEXT STEPS

The activities of WP4 are mostly completed with the delivery of the app expected for Autumn 2019. The results of the WP4 activities are feeding into the definition of the demonstrations (WP8) and also of the exploitation plans (WP9).

5 Work Package 5 FreeWheel process design

5.1 OBJECTIVES

WP5 aims to address comprehensively the design of the manufacturing process by selecting the best set of technologies to be employed for a specific product as well as defining the process parameters and precedence constraints, which will be then sequenced to create a process chain in accordance to a number of strategies (e.g. productivity, energy efficiency and accuracy).

5.2 ACTIVITIES

The work package focused on the following activities:

- Designing process parameters for AM and ablation technologies associated to Round Robin Parts and final prototypes.
- Ensuring the transformation of CAD files to NC interoperable and processable files.
- Incorporating the process modelling in the machine design, also identifying the requirements for the handling, tooling and sensing systems to be configured in WP6.

5.2.1 Process parameters design

The team of project FreeWheel incorporates expertise in advanced Additive Manufacturing technologies and processes, matured within previous and concurrent projects. This is complemented by advanced knowledge of commercial polymer 3D printing technology to be applied both to structural and aesthetic parts design and production. The library of features and associated process parameters for Direct Energy Deposition and ablation has been referred to once identified the geometrical characteristics of the customised FreeWheel connectors, to highlight gaps in the knowledge acquired. Once the customised connectors have undergone final checks on structural performance and manufacturability (WP3), production runs will provide the final validation of the process parameters identified on the basis of the geometries to be produced.

5.2.2 Transforming the CAD files into interoperable and processable CNC files

Because of the intrinsic characteristics of the AM production process, production strategies are to be implemented to ensure that the item produced respects, amongst others, the geometrical dimensions of the design, i.e. the CAD file. This is ensured through the implementation of off line and on line design and processing strategies. With respect to the off line strategies, manufacturability analysis is conducted to identify building direction, infill, layer thickness etc. Amongst the on line strategies is the regenerative CAx chain, whereby a closed loop control checks regularly the build up of the piece against the design – already a

version of the original part design modified to account for e.g. finishing and/or thermal deformations of the piece – and generates adapted production follow-up steps to redress over- or under-deposition. For aesthetic parts design, the team is exploiting the opportunities given by the FDM technology to design innovative and eye catching pieces.

5.2.3 Incorporating the process modelling in the machine design

To complement the experience gained by the team with previous studies on Round Robin Parts, project FreeWheel will undertake production runs on the customised connectors to validate the process parameters associated with the features already known and to study optimisation of production times and energy and material efficiencies, thus working towards the Technical Development Objectives related to lead time and environmental performance of the production.

5.3 NEXT STEPS

Work package 5 will last up to the end of the year 2019 and will concentrate on the validation of the production process and equipment for both metal and polymer material parts of the FreeWheel solution. As the work package focuses on optimising the production of the customised connectors, activities will concentrate not only in delivering the parts for the final demonstrators but also in ensuring the objectives of the FreeWheel service in terms of environmental impact and customer satisfaction are met.

6 Work Package 6 FreeWheel production infrastructure design

6.1 OBJECTIVES

Work package 6 deals with the production infrastructure supporting the manufacturing of the FreeWheel parts in metal and plastic Additive Manufacturing. The general objectives of the current work package refer to:

- Customization of the mechatronic equipment to accomplish the production KPIs covering stand-alone resources, devices and systems to support metal and plastic based AM technologies both laser assisted and not.
- Designing of the sensing system for process and equipment monitoring.
- Development of the automation and communication platforms to ensure the control, coordination, synchronization and supervision of the entire production infrastructure.

6.2 ACTIVITIES

6.2.1 Design and development of distributed production infrastructure

Based on the requirements defined in WP3 (Product design), together with the information gathered in WP5 Process design, in WP6 Production infrastructure, several resources have been investigated and integrated. In this task, therefore, the project team took stock of the existing production infrastructure available to the consortium in terms of equipment for metal working, considering with WP5 the processing capabilities and starting to review the configuration objectives and the requisites for architecture, features, performance and tolerable resource utilization. A commercial 3D printing system was modified to make available to the equipment portfolio an "under vacuum" additive manufacturing process dedicated to carbon-fibre-reinforced polymers. These modifications allow to improve mechanical properties of 3D printed products, and to achieve a stable and reliable AM process.

Once defined, the configuration objectives and requisites for process and architecture were matched with the information about the real machines, well characterised by the team in this and previous or concurrent projects.

6.2.2 Design and development of the sensing system

The available sensing system mounted on the equipment portfolio has been reviewed to understand the properties currently monitored. To guarantee the monitoring of the process according to the requirement of the KPIs of the project, the team is exploring the feasibility of adding further modifications and/or measurement protocols.

6.2.3 Design and development of the automation solution

The production machines are equipped with sensors enabling the implementation of the deposition strategies identified in WP5.

6.3 NEXT STEPS

The equipment will be tested, together with the process (WP5) on the final customised connectors, currently undergoing performance and manufacturability review within WP3.

7 Work Package 7 FreeWheel integration and lifecycle distributed management and optimization

7.1 OBJECTIVES

The work package deals with the integration and optimisation of the FreeWheel solution over time.

7.2 ACTIVITIES

Only the first task of this work package started during Year Two of the project. This task deals with the integration of the FreeWheel solution components and activities focused on the definition of the technical specifications of the rack. The rack is currently conceived to perform the functions of holding and recharging the motorisation unit and enabling the connection and disconnection of the unit to the user's wheelchair. The main issue to be solved is the design of a rack able to cope with very different widths of wheelchairs. This is particularly relevant for the connection and disconnection functionality.

Other activities within task 7.1 focused on finalising the integration of the hardware and software part of the FreeWheel solution, feeding into the design of the app within WP4.

7.3 NEXT STEPS

The WP will focus on ensuring optimal equipment set-up and ramp-up and overall efficiency of the functioning of the FreeWheel system.

8 Work Package 9 FreeWheel dissemination and exploitation

8.1 OBJECTIVES

This work package focuses on ensuring the results of the project are shared amongst peers and stakeholders and are used to progress further the innovation

8.2 ACTIVITES

The team focused on delivering scientific communications, articles and papers as well as taking part in awareness raising activities, including regular presence on Twitter through the @EUFreeWheel profile. An acceleration has been given to the exploitation activities following on from the comments received at the Review Meeting.

8.2.1 Scientific dissemination

Activity on scientific dissemination of the results of the project has intensified in Year Two as the solution takes form and interesting outcomes are materialising and innovative methodologies have been applied successfully.

In the second year of the project, the following papers were submitted and accepted either for publication or for presentation at conferences:

- In June 2019, Keen Bull and IRIS submitted a paper to the III International Congress on Technology and Tourism for All. The paper has been accepted for publication in the proceedings
- In July 2019, LMS presented the paper "Context awareness system in the use phase of a smart mobility platform: A vision system for a light-weight approach" to the 13th CIRP Conference on Intelligent Computation in Manufacturing Engineering" in Naples, Italy
- In August 2019, Keen Bull and Genny Angels presented a paper titled "Multi-disciplinary and lean innovation for assistive technologies" to the World Health Organisation's GREAT Consultation 2019- Improving access to assistive technology for everyone, everywhere in Geneva, Switzerland
- LMS submitted a paper to the 8th CIRP Conference on Assembly Technologies and Systems (May 2020) titled "Parametric design for 3D printed plastic panel as a decorative part of a mobility platform".

8.2.2 Industrial promotion

Many awareness raising initiatives involving the end users and/or stakeholders from the specific Assistive Technologies sector. Since last Review Meeting, Genny Angels participated to the organisation of the Swim games in Albisola, Italy, where mobility issues for wheelchair users were highlighted.

The Twitter account established for the project in January 2019 is being regularly fed and it is steadily gaining popularity. The project website is being updated with the main events of the project and reports also all public project deliverables and open access papers.

An article describing the project appeared on the July issue of the Project Repository Journal.

8.2.3 Exploitation program definition

The team held two workshops (May 2019 in SUPSI and September 2019 in Morphica) to set up the business plan of the FreeWheel solution and to plan ahead to the exploitation of the main result of the project, i.e. the FreeWheel mobility solution. Interest from industrial partners has been gathered and the first opportunities for funding and investment have been identified. Such activities are feeding into a preliminary exploitation plan being completed (confidential document).

8.3 NEXT STEPS

The team is continuing the dissemination and awareness raising activities. The team identified the conferences and events in Year Three relevant to the project. The academic partners are also gearing up to define possible outputs for scientific publications on the final results of the project. Two more articles are planned on the Project Repository Journal, one for the January 2020 issue and one for the late summer-early autumn of 2020.

Opportunities for clustering with other FOF projects have been explored, including at least one event of presentation of a few projects participated by the project partners (e.g. 4dHybrid, ManuSquare and others) to industrial clusters, e.g. the one represented by partner IAM and other candidates.

Activity on Twitter is continuing and so are participations to awareness raising initiatives particularly directed to the end users and the sector of assistive technologies and medical devices.

The project team is working on the refining of the business model and the cost analysis to support the development of a business plan to be used to gather the interest of potential investors. The list of participants to the Business Interest Group is being built up.

9 Activities to be started for Work Package 8 FreeWheel demonstration

The technical activities of the final year of the project gear up to the final demonstration of the solution. This demonstration will take place in Patras, at the Castle, and in Beinasco, near Turin, in a shopping mall.

The team has visited the site in Beinasco to gather information on space availability and logistics. At the 5th GA, a proposal for the indicative period of the two demos was discussed as well as details about the information required by all parties involved to kick start the planning of the activities. The final dates will be shortly communicated to the EU.

10 Gender equality actions

No changes are reported with respect to the gender equality issues within the project as no staff changes have taken place in the Second Year of the project.

Table. 1 below shows the composition of the team working for the FreeWheel project within each of the beneficiaries and in total within the Consortium. The balance of 49% female and 51% male members of staff at the end of Year One has been confirmed for Year Two.

	1 st October 2017		1 st October 2018		1 st October 2019	
Beneficiaries	Number of female in the Freewheel team	Number of male in the FreeWheel team	Number of female in the Freewheel team	Number of male in the FreeWheel team	Number of female in the Freewheel team	Number of male in the FreeWheel team
1 - IRIS SRL	4	1	4	1	4	1
2 - MORPHICA SOCIETA A RESPONSABILITA LIMITATA SEMPLIFICATA A SOCIO UNICO	1	1	1	2	1	2
3 - KEEN BULL SAGL	1	2	2	3	2	3
4 - MCH-TRONICS SAGL	1	2	1	2	1	2
5 - KUMO TECHNOLOGIES SL	0	1	1	1	1	1
6 - INNOVAZIONE AUTOMOTIVE E METALMECCANICA SCARL	1	0	1	0	1	0
6a - LAZZERINI	1	1	1	1	1	1
7 - GENNY ANGELS	0	2	1	2	1	2
8 - SCUOLA UNIVERSITARIA PROFESSIONALE DELLA SVIZZERA ITALIANA	2	1	2	4	2	4
9 - PANEPISTIMIO PATRON - LMS	0	2	1	5	1	5
10 - NETWORK SOCIETY RESEARCH LTD	0	1	0	1	0	1
11 - EPHORATE OF ANTIQUITIES OF ACHAIA	2	1	3	1	3	1

WHOLE CONSORTIUM	13	16	18	19	18	19
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Table. 1 Gender composition of FreeWheel team at the start of the project and after Year One

11 Conclusions

Year Two of project FreeWheel saw the peak of technical activity for the project, with most of the work packages active and delivering results constituting the stepping stones for the final demonstration of the FreeWheel mobility solution.

The results of WP2, which ended at Month 12, fed into the definition of the FreeWheel solution in its two main parts, i.e. the motorising unit (WP3) and the mobile application (WP4). Those and the racks currently under development (WP7) support the delivery of the FreeWheel service. The latter has been mapped out and analysed (WP4) providing important inputs both for the definition of the integration of the elements of the solution and for the definition of the business model supporting the delivery of the service.

The details of the motorising unit, and specifically the customised connectors are the testing ground for the knowledge on processes (WP5) and equipment (WP6) acquired by the team during the years and to be refined within FreeWheel to implement strategies of manufacturing granting the most efficient and rapid production.

FreeWheel mobility solution is an innovation gathering interests amongst the end user hence the team is accelerating on the definition of exploitation actions to bring the solution closer to the market.

Year Three will focus on finalising all the results of the technical activities towards the demonstration of the solution in Patras and in Turin.